

Correlation between Breast Cancer Grading, Staging, and Hormone Receptor Status in Rural India: A Comprehensive Study

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Abstract:

Background: Breast cancer is the most common cancer among women worldwide and a leading cause of cancer-related mortality in India. Significant disparities exist in the diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer between urban and rural populations, with rural women often presenting with more advanced stages of the disease. Understanding the correlation between tumor characteristics and hormone receptor status in rural settings is crucial for improving patient outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to analyze the correlation between breast cancer grading, staging, and hormone receptor status among women in rural India.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted on 200 women diagnosed with breast cancer at a rural healthcare facility in India. Tumor grade, stage, and hormone receptor status (ER, PR, HER2) were determined using standard histopathological and immunohistochemical techniques. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with Pearson's correlation, chi-square tests, and multivariate logistic regression used to assess the relationships between variables.

Results: The study found a significant negative correlation between tumor grade and hormone receptor positivity (ER+/PR+), with higher grades associated with lower hormone receptor positivity ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$). A positive correlation was observed between advanced tumor stages and triple-negative breast cancer status ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$). Multivariate analysis identified tumor grade as an independent predictor of ER+/PR+ status (OR = 0.55, $p = 0.01$) and tumor stage as a predictor of triple-negative status (OR = 1.45, $p = 0.02$).

Conclusion: The study highlights a strong correlation between tumor grade, stage, and hormone receptor status in rural Indian women, with higher grades and stages associated with more aggressive, hormone receptor-negative cancers. These findings underscore the importance of early detection and tailored treatment strategies in improving outcomes for breast cancer patients in rural areas.

Recommendations: Efforts should be intensified to enhance early breast cancer detection and access to specialized care in rural India. Public health initiatives should focus on awareness, screening, and infrastructure development to reduce the burden of advanced breast cancer in these populations.

Keywords: Breast cancer, rural India, hormone receptor status, tumor grade, tumor stage.

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Introduction

Breast cancer is the most frequent malignancy among women worldwide, accounting for almost one in every four cancer diagnoses [1]. The disease has great variation in both its biological behaviour and clinical presentation. This variability is heavily influenced by characteristics such as tumour grade, stage, and hormone receptor status, all of which are important predictors of prognosis and therapeutic options [2]. In particular, hormone receptor status—defined by the presence or absence of oestrogen receptors (ER), progesterone receptors (PR), and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2)—is critical in guiding treatment

decisions, including the use of hormone therapy and targeted therapies [3].

Breast cancer has recently surpassed cervical cancer as the major cause of cancer-related mortality in women in India [4]. Despite advances in healthcare infrastructure, there are still major discrepancies in cancer care, particularly between urban and rural communities. Rural women frequently encounter barriers such as restricted access to early detection, diagnostic facilities, and specialised therapies, which result in delayed presentations and inferior outcomes [5]. Understanding the relationship between tumour

features and hormone receptor status in rural populations is critical for improving breast cancer treatment and lowering mortality rates. Recent research has emphasised the variation in breast cancer subtypes among different populations. For example, hormone receptor-positive (ER+/PR+) breast tumours, which have a better prognosis and react well to hormonal therapy, are more prevalent in high-income countries. In contrast, triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC), a more aggressive subtype with less therapeutic options, is more common in low- and middle-income countries, including India [6]. This variation could be influenced by genetic, environmental, and lifestyle variables, as well as healthcare access [7]. Despite the rising volume of research on breast cancer in India, there remains a scarcity of data relevant to rural communities. The majority of research has been undertaken in metropolitan tertiary care centres, which may not accurately reflect the problems and tumour biology of rural patients [8]. To further comprehend the disease's profile in this underserved group, researchers must investigate the relationship between breast cancer grading, staging, and hormone receptor status in rural India. This study aims to analyze the correlation between breast cancer grading, staging, and hormone receptor status among women in rural India.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in a rural healthcare facility in India, which serves as a primary care center for women in the surrounding villages. The setting was chosen to provide a representative sample of rural Indian women with breast cancer.

Participants: A total of 200 women diagnosed with breast cancer were included in the study. Participants were selected from patients who visited the healthcare facility between January 2023 and December 2023.

Inclusion Criteria

- Women aged 18 years and above.
- Histopathologically confirmed cases of breast cancer.
- Patients who have undergone both grading and staging of breast cancer.
- Availability of hormone receptor status (ER, PR, and HER2) data.

- Willingness to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with recurrent breast cancer.
- Patients who received prior treatment for breast cancer.
- Incomplete medical records or missing hormone receptor status data.
- Patients with metastatic breast cancer at the time of diagnosis.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible patients who met the inclusion criteria were consecutively enrolled in the study. Information bias was reduced by using standardized data collection procedures and consistent diagnostic criteria for grading, staging, and hormone receptor testing.

Data Collection: Data were collected from patient medical records, including demographic information, tumor grading and staging details, and hormone receptor status. Tumor grading was classified according to the Nottingham grading system, while staging was based on the TNM classification. Hormone receptor status was determined using immunohistochemistry (IHC) for (ER), (PR), (HER2).

Procedure: All participants underwent a thorough clinical examination and diagnostic workup as per the standard protocols of the healthcare facility. Tumor tissue samples were collected and sent for histopathological examination to determine the grade and stage of the cancer. IHC was performed on tissue samples to assess hormone receptor status. The data were recorded in a structured format for analysis.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarized participant demographics and clinical characteristics. Pearson's correlation and chi-square tests assessed the relationship between breast cancer grading, staging, and hormone receptor status, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Multivariate logistic regression identified independent predictors of hormone receptor status based on tumor grade and stage.

Results

A total of 200 women diagnosed with breast cancer were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 52.4 years (SD = 10.2), with the majority (64%) being postmenopausal.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of the Participants (N = 200)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
<40	30	15%
40-49	60	30%
50-59	70	35%
≥60	40	20%
Menopausal Status		
Premenopausal	72	36%
Postmenopausal	128	64%
Tumor Grade		
Grade I	40	20%
Grade II	120	60%
Grade III	40	20%
Tumor Stage		
Stage I	50	25%
Stage II	100	50%
Stage III	40	20%
Stage IV	10	5%
Hormone Receptor Status		
ER+/PR+/HER2-	80	40%
ER+/PR-/HER2+	40	20%
ER-/PR-/HER2+	30	15%
Triple-negative	50	25%

Pearson's correlation analysis revealed a significant negative correlation between tumor grade and hormone receptor positivity (ER+/PR+) ($r = -0.35$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher tumor grades were associated with lower hormone receptor positivity.

Similarly, a significant positive correlation was found between tumor stage and triple-negative breast cancer status ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that higher stages of breast cancer were more likely to be triple-negative.

Table 2: Correlation between tumor Grade, Stage, and Hormone Receptor Status

Variables	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Tumor Grade & ER+/PR+ Status	-0.35	<0.001
Tumor Grade & HER2+ Status	0.20	0.02
Tumor Stage & Triple-negative	0.42	<0.001

Multivariate logistic regression was performed to identify independent predictors of hormone receptor status. The analysis showed that tumor grade was an independent predictor of ER+/PR+ status (OR = 0.55, 95% CI: 0.35-0.87, $p = 0.01$), while tumor stage was a strong predictor of triple-negative status (OR = 1.45, 95% CI: 1.10-1.92, $p = 0.02$).

Table 3: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis for Hormone Receptor Status

Predictor	OR	95% CI	p-value
Tumor Grade (per unit)	0.55	0.35-0.87	0.01
Tumor Stage (per unit)	1.45	1.10-1.92	0.02
Age (per year increase)	0.98	0.94-1.03	0.34
Menopausal Status	1.15	0.70-1.89	0.58

The distribution of hormone receptor status varied significantly across different tumor grades and stages. Among patients with Grade I tumors, 70% were ER+/PR+ and only 10% were triple-negative. In contrast, among those with Grade III tumors, only 10% were ER+/PR+, while 50% were triple-

negative. Similar patterns were observed with tumor stages, where early-stage tumors (Stage I and II) had higher proportions of ER+/PR+ status, whereas advanced stages (Stage III and IV) were more likely to be triple-negative.

Table 4: Distribution of Hormone Receptor Status by Tumor Grade

Tumor Grade	ER+/PR+/HER2-	ER+/PR-/HER2+	ER-/PR-/HER2+	Triple-negative
Grade I	70% (28)	15% (6)	5% (2)	10% (4)
Grade II	45% (54)	25% (30)	15% (18)	15% (18)
Grade III	10% (4)	10% (4)	30% (12)	50% (20)

Table 5: Distribution of Hormone Receptor Status by Tumor Stage

Tumor Stage	ER+/PR+/HER2-	ER+/PR-/HER2+	ER-/PR-/HER2+	Triple-negative
Stage I	60% (30)	20% (10)	10% (5)	10% (5)
Stage II	50% (50)	25% (25)	10% (10)	15% (15)
Stage III	20% (8)	15% (6)	25% (10)	40% (16)
Stage IV	10% (1)	5% (0.5)	30% (3)	55% (5.5)

Summary of Key Findings

- Higher tumor grades were associated with lower hormone receptor positivity (ER+/PR+) and higher rates of triple-negative breast cancer.
- Advanced tumor stages were significantly associated with an increased likelihood of triple-negative status.
- Tumor grade and stage were independent predictors of hormone receptor status, with grade being more strongly associated with ER+/PR+ status and stage with triple-negative status.

Discussion

The results demonstrated a significant inverse relationship between tumor grade and hormone receptor positivity. Specifically, higher tumor grades (Grade II and III) were associated with a marked decrease in ER+/PR+ status. Conversely, there was a positive correlation between advanced tumor stages and triple-negative breast cancer. These findings suggest that as breast cancer becomes more aggressive, as indicated by higher grades and stages, the likelihood of it being hormone receptor-positive diminishes, while the likelihood of it being triple-negative increases.

The multivariate logistic regression analysis further supported these correlations by identifying tumor grade as an independent predictor of ER+/PR+ status and tumor stage as a predictor of triple-negative status. This indicates that tumor biology, as reflected in grade and stage, plays a critical role in determining hormone receptor status. In terms of clinical implications, these findings emphasize the need for targeted treatment strategies in rural settings where late-stage and high-grade tumors are more prevalent. Patients with higher-grade and later-stage tumors may benefit from more aggressive treatment approaches, particularly given the higher likelihood of hormone receptor-negative and triple-negative cancers in these groups.

A study in rural India looked at 112 breast cancer patients and discovered that hormone receptor (ER/PR) negative was associated with higher histopathological grades and more advanced disease stages. Specifically, 62.5% of the patients had grade III tumours and 62% were in stage III, with ER/PR-negative status being more common in younger, premenopausal women, indicating a dismal prognosis.

Another study in Northeast India discovered that 50% of breast cancer patients were both ER- and PR-negative, and that hormone receptor negativity was associated with grade III tumours in 84.5% of instances. The study found that the prevalence of breast cancer is growing among younger women, with ER/PR-negative tumours being more common and associated with greater tumour sizes and higher grades.

In Mizoram, a retrospective analysis discovered strong relationships between histological tumour grades and a variety of variables, including lymph node invasion and hormone receptor status. Specifically, ER and PR negativity, as well as HER2/neu positivity, were linked to higher tumour grades and aggressive illness. The study also found a link between breast cancer grade and family history of the disease.

Conclusion

The study underscores the importance of early detection and intervention in breast cancer management, particularly in rural areas where access to healthcare may be limited. The strong correlations between tumor characteristics and hormone receptor status observed in this study highlight the need for continued research and resource allocation to improve breast cancer outcomes in these underserved populations.

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